

Hybrid Social Entrepreneurship: A New Form of Capitalism to Enhance Local Economic Development in South Africa

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This paper aims to analyse how hybrid social entrepreneurship as a new form of capitalism could potentially attempt to enhance LED. This paper argues that hybrid social entrepreneurship as a new form or version of capitalism would offer innovative and comprehensive ways of improving LED. Because social and economic conundrums such as poverty, unemployment and inequality never expire as long as the destitute continues to endure such inhumane conditions and poor living standards. It is necessary because liberal capitalism fails to comprehensively improve LED. This is because of the shortfalls of both public and private sectors and the arrogance of liberal capitalism. Thus, the paper adopts a literature-based methodology wherein secondary data sources were used to achieve the aim of the paper. Thus, capitalism on its own seeks to benefits only the minority, bourgeoisie, and the privileged and focus on profits over improving the social well-being of the underserved communities. To corroborate and ensure that LED benefits the most underprivileged individuals, hybrid social entrepreneurship as a new form of capitalism should be embraced. It finds that the hybrid social enterprises as a form of capitalism that encompass both for-profit and non-profit legal structure offers a promising intervention that could salvage the limitations of capitalism which solely relies on profit. Hence, to drive both social and economic change to enhance LED, hybrid social entrepreneurs may reinvest their profits in social programs and foster economic and human development.

Keywords: Capitalism, local economic development, hybrid social entrepreneurship, poverty, South Africa

When dissecting the good and bad sides of capitalism, Baumol, Litan and Schramm (2007) contend that capitalism is not a singular type of economic system; instead, it manifests in various forms that vary significantly regarding their effects on economic development and the eradication of poverty. The unspoken belief behind the concept of a uniform capitalism, the idea that all capitalist economies are essentially alike, mirrors the mindset prevalent during the Cold War when two superpowers, embodying two major ideologies, contested for the allegiance and support of global populations (Litan & Schramm, 2007). For that reason, this paper contends that to salvage and arrest the global predicaments that threaten economic growth and development, particularly for third-world countries, hybrid social entrepreneurship as a new form of capitalism brings a new breath of fresh air. Thus, the domain of hybrid social entrepreneurship is rapidly evolving in both practical applications and academic circles. The number and diversity of entities identified as hybrid social entrepreneurship initiatives are increasing alongside the topic (Certo & Miller, 2008; Ibarra-Vazquez, Ramirez-Montoya, & Miranda, 2023). Therefore, up until now, there are no universally accepted definitions of what constitutes a social entrepreneur in both practice and academic settings.

The discussion concerning the definition of hybrid social entrepreneurship continues to be active. Instead of launching a business

solely for-profit maximization, hybrid social entrepreneurs initiate a venture to generate a more significant impact and benefit for society (Ibarra-Vazquez et al., 2023). Additionally, hybrid social entrepreneurs may focus on a single aim, which is to address certain socioeconomic issues and create a business as a means of aiding in the improvement of local economic development and quality of life (Popkova, Bogoviz, Lobova, Delo, Sergi, & Yankovskaya, 2023). In the context of this paper, hybrid social entrepreneurs are individuals who have their own private business that maximizes profit and also reinvest their profits towards improving the social welfare of the country. One could imply that hybrid social entrepreneurship in South Africa embodies a revolutionary model of capitalism, blending profit intentions with social influence to foster community economic growth. This model tackles systemic disparities and historical economic marginalization by emphasizing community empowerment in conjunction with financial viability.

The main reason is that hybrid social entrepreneurs have noted the disparities and shortcomings in both the public and private sectors regarding the provision of good job opportunities and the improvement of human development for the impoverished and working-class individuals (Kamaludin, 2023). Essentially, social enterprises occupy a space between the private and public sectors. They can be viewed as functioning within the third sector and the social and solidarity economy. Although social enterprises positively impact economic growth and welfare, the development of hybrid social entrepreneurship is currently advancing at a rather slow pace (Akhter, Hossain, & Asheq, 2020). This background poses an important question for scholars and politicians to understand how effectively the growth of hybrid social entrepreneurship can be accelerated to promote Local Economic Development (LED).

Problem Statement

The paper aimed to examine and analyse how hybrid social entrepreneurship could be a new form of capitalism in trying to

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enhance LED. The central problem in this paper is that liberal capitalism as well as government continues to be sluggish in improving LED. Most authors have conceptualized LED and have attempted to provide recommendations on how to enhance LED through various interventions and strategies. To date, the question of how to enhance LED is still up for debate. However, the role that the government and private sector play in the economy should not be downplayed because they try their level best to arrest socioeconomic ills that the destitute endure daily. What is challenging is that despite all the interventions from both public and private sectors, social and economic challenges persist due to liberal capitalism embedded in the government and private sector. Thus, hybrid social entrepreneurship could offer potential solutions to the proletariat and working class grappling with triple injustices (poverty, unemployment & inequality) (Pillay, 2001; Habiyaemye, King, & Tregenna, 2022). Because hybrid social entrepreneurs through their dual mission which tackles both social and economic could be a new version of capitalism that cares not only about economic growth, but also human development. Hence, there is a need to explore the subject of hybrid social entrepreneurship to enhance LED.

Method

This is a conceptual paper that has adopted a literature-based methodology. This means that literature was reviewed with regard to the subject under investigation. Therefore, secondary data was collected through journal articles, internet sources, books, reports and other secondary publications to achieve the aim of the paper. Meanwhile, a thematic analysis was used to analyse and interpret secondary data sources. Braun and Clarke (2012: 2) describe thematic analysis as “accessible, flexible, and increasingly popular method of qualitative data analysis”. Through its flexibility, the researcher(s) developed relevant themes for the paper and the interpretation was provided thereof.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Foundations- The Paradoxical Nature of Dual Mission in Social Enterprises

Paradox Theory in business and management explores how contradictory elements can coexist and even rely on each other in organisations (Ciambotti, Pedrini, Doherty, & Molteni, 2023; StudySmarter, n.d). Social enterprises, as hybrid organisations, effectively merge financial and social objectives to achieve both profit and social responsibility (Glaveli & Geormas, 2018). This theory highlights the importance of managing conflicting elements within businesses and organisational networks (Glaveli & Geormas, 2018; Saebi, Foss, & Linder, 2019). The authors acknowledged the paradoxical essence ingrained in these establishments, as social duty and making profit are conflicting, yet interconnected fundamental aspects of social enterprises (Battilana & Lee, 2014; Hahn & Knight, 2021; Peek, 2022; White, Samuel, Peattie, & Doherty, 2022). The significance of this theory in the paper is significant because the paper focuses on hybrid social entrepreneurs who pursue a social and economic mission. However, the dual mission of hybrid social entrepreneurship or theory is crucial to ensure the success of the business and also contribute to the social economy, thus improving LED.

In the field of management studies, the idea of paradox first emerged in the late 1970s and early 1980s when it was proposed as a

useful lens for examining organisational events (Carmine & De Marchi, 2023). Knowing that the paradox theory may be quite helpful, either one is studying for an educational program in business studies or just wants to expand their knowledge. This school of thinking can help to understand the intricate dynamics that exist within firms and their environments and is highly significant in the fields of organisational theory and managerial strategy (Carmine & De Marchi, 2023). The theory is linked to the paper due to its relevance in linking social and economic mission, which should coexist to ensure the sustainability of the enterprises and ultimately form the basis for a new form of capitalism. Even in social enterprises, the paradox theory is useful for resolving conflicts between social fulfilment and long-term financial viability.

The challenge for social enterprises is to fulfil their social objective while also making sure that their operations can be sustained financially (Samuel, 2018). Andriopoulos and Lewis (2009) contend that organisational components in opposition paradoxes are sensible when seen separately, yet they become not useful and illogical when they occur simultaneously. In essence, the latter authors emphasise that different traditions (social & economic) make sense when they work together for the sustainability of the organisation. Hence, the Social Business Initiative's European Union (2011) description of social enterprise highlights the challenge of balancing some key dimensions in social enterprises' mission: (i) the primary focus is on social goals and (ii) also engaging in economic activities to meet commercial objectives.

Social enterprises must navigate competing priorities like balancing short-term profits with long-term viability, cutting costs while maintaining quality, searching for new opportunities while utilising current strengths, and finding a balance between stability and innovation (Ketkar & Puri, 2022). Companies must also consider social and economic aspects that could work together in a comprehensive way to ensure the sustainability of the business. Thus, paradox theory suggests that goals that appear to be incompatible, such as creating social and economic value, can exist together, perhaps to represent a new version of capitalism. Therefore, organisations that embrace and accept multiple goals are more successful in managing conflicting demands than those that seek to resolve trade-offs (Hahn & Knight, 2021). The notion of paradox has been extensively studied in relation to mission-profit paradox management and hybrid social entrepreneurship studies (Cherrier, Goswami, & Ray, 2018; Smith & Besharov, 2019). Smith, Marya, Anke, and Michael (2012) and Sarhangi, Mashayekhi, Souzanchi, and Kashani (2021) propose that contradictions can be controlled by employing a tactic of separating and integrating the social and business components of the organisation, followed by fostering collaboration through various mechanisms. However, other scholars, including Siegner, Pinkse, and Panwar (2018) and Besharov, Smith, and Darabi (2019) note that it is more efficient to accept the dual mission at the same time rather than dividing and then integrating opposing reasoning. For this reason, there is a sense in which dividing social and economic aspects in a business can lead to ineffective business operation. Rather, hybrid social entrepreneurship encompasses the dual demands of social and economic aspects to form a new version of capitalism which could holistically enhance LED.

A study by Ketkar and Puri (2022) links the theory to leadership. In their study, they found that a large portion of the early research on leadership in SEs in relation to the theory concentrated on the

experiences, motives, networking, and communication skills of the hybrid social entrepreneurship, frequently depicting these individuals as champions. Leaders who are typically hybrid social entrepreneurs play a crucial role in making sure that social enterprises fulfil their mission and achieve their dual objectives of financial resilience and social value. For that reason, the "paradoxical leadership" concept, made known by Smith et al. (2012) outlines the competencies that hybrid social entrepreneurship needs to have to handle social and financial pressures. Therefore, leadership and organisational management are paramount to ensure execution in both social and economic endeavours. Therefore, Yesmin, Kohar, Hira, and Moshiul (2021) argue that due to the incomplete understanding of what actually constitutes the concept of hybrid social entrepreneurship the mechanisms involved in leadership and managing paradoxes resulting from competing objectives remain a topic of interest for hybrid social entrepreneurship studies. Sarhangi, Mashayekhi, and Souzanchi (2024) discovered that leaders (hybrid social entrepreneurs) switched their focus between their organisation's social and economic divisions. Smith et al. (2016) show that this is necessary to achieve dual goals in the long term. In the context of the paper, 'leaders' should be seen as hybrid social entrepreneurs who are also the owners of social enterprises.

The Relevance, Challenges and Gaps in Theory

The theory is very pertinent in the paper because it provides and holds the view that social enterprises should act as a new form of capitalism to embrace both social and economic missions (hybrid), which are elucidated in the paper. It is directly related to the paper because the paper argues that social enterprises must fulfil social and economic missions to build a sustainable LED and alternatively act as a new form of capitalism. This is despite the different arguments from different scholars regarding the conceptualization of social enterprises. Consequently, the paper is firm on its definition. The theory also provides a direction to the paper by critiquing the dual mission of social enterprises. Yet, one major danger for organisations with hybrid (dual mission) structures (social & economic) is drifting their objectives. Social enterprises may unintentionally lose sight of their social objectives as they become increasingly commercial to remain financially viable (Forbes, 2015; Samuel, 2018). This change might result in a less social effect since the organisation will now put income generation ahead when it comes to the public. One example of mission deviance is when the organisation's primary goal is jeopardized by prioritising financial benefits over social goals. The difficulty is in striking a balance that does not compromise the goals of social efficacy or economic sustainability (Samuel, 2018). One may not highlight challenges without suggesting some possible alternatives that could aid in striking a balance between social and economic missions. Not as a conclusion, however, as a suggestion that a clear definition of the mission of the organisations should be clarified. This clarity is critical because it would facilitate the successful alignment of resources and efforts to accomplish both goals. Also, leadership and management, as noted and suggested by Ketkar and Puri (2022) in the discussion above, could be a panacea to balancing the social and economic impact of social enterprises.

Terminologies Describing Hybrid Social Entrepreneurship

The description of hybrid social entrepreneurship varies from one

person to another and is defined in different contexts. Thus, to date, there is no universally agreed description of hybrid social entrepreneurship. Which means that the concept of hybrid social entrepreneurship is up for further exploration. However, in the context of this paper, hybrid social entrepreneurs are described by their value creation (social & economic). Such a description is illustrated on the figure below.

Figure 1

Value Creation by Social Entrepreneurs

Note. Source: (Authors' own compilation)

The aim of social missions is to create positive, enduring change that innovatively addresses social challenges. Al Najem and de Vré (2023) argue that social missions are the primary catalysts for social business existence and guide the generation of positive change in addressing social issues through innovative and sustainable approaches. Hybrid social entrepreneurs' commitment to the organization's goal guarantees the execution of their intended activities and strategies. Social value mainly focuses not on profit but on fulfilling essential needs such as food, water, shelter, education, and healthcare for the disadvantaged in society (Dzomonda, 2021). The social significance of this paper pertains to the reduction of poverty and comprehensive enhancement of LED. As a result, social enterprises are viewed as crucial for development and alleviating poverty (Abeysekera, 2019; Matebese, 2022). Poverty is characterized in different ways and is perceived from several perspectives. It is often claimed that poverty ought to be based on logical arguments and scientific data; however, there is no universally recognized scientific definition, as it is essentially a political concept and thus, one that is naturally open to discussion.

Dual-Purpose or Hybrid Business Models

The nature of hybrid social entrepreneurship could be described in its operation, which is known to be a 'dual mission' or hybrid business model. Contrary to traditional entrepreneurs and liberal capitalism, hybrid social entrepreneurs are exclusive in the sense that they are also the protagonists of human development. This model (hybrid) contests traditional capitalism by incorporating social goals directly into business practices instead of regarding social impact as a secondary outcome or charitable approach. It establishes a self-perpetuating circle where economic endeavours support social objectives and social aims inspire creative economic strategies (Mongelli, Rullani, Ramus, & Rimal, 2019). This method may result in more fair and sustainable local economies by integrating social value creation into the liberal capitalist system (Starnawska, 2015).

Social Value

In the UK, the Public Services (Social Value) Act (2013) defines social value and requires all public sector entities and their suppliers to consider beyond the financial value of an agreement in assessing how the products and services they procure can improve the economic, social and environmental welfare of a community (Local Government Association, 2024). Thus, social value encompasses all the benefits resulting from any endeavour, business, or initiative that extend beyond the direct economic effects of the venture (i.e., the revenue it generates minus the costs of completing the project (Louise-Fellowes, n.d). Instances of social value encompass elements like the presence of communal spaces, parks, and libraries, along with support and engagement in local groups. Hybrid social entrepreneurship can help municipalities develop a holistic LED strategy by utilizing existing technologies to enhance the profitability of their businesses. Thus, a portion of their earnings might be allocated to social initiatives to enhance LED and social economy more significantly.

The Whatimpact Enterprises report (2024) shows that social value projects aim to enhance the standard of living and well-being of individuals and communities. Examples of this include community engagement initiatives, donations to charity, volunteer efforts, support for social causes (such as healthcare, education & poverty alleviation), and actions to promote diversity, equity and inclusion within the organization. This entails creating links, understanding the community's needs and objectives, and collaborating to address the community's challenges and opportunities together (The Whatimpact Enterprises, 2024). There are multiple methods to engage the community, including partnering with local organizations, joining local events and taking part in decision-making discussions. In the business sector, the creation of social value is often known as Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Essentially, social values focus on achieving measurable objectives that will serve the community and society at large (Compliance Chain, 2024). It explores how programs might aid local communities by enhancing access to services and opportunities, thereby improving living standards for residents (Compliance Chain, 2024).

Hybrid social entrepreneurs can enhance the connections between their businesses and stakeholders by focusing on social value (Kickul & Lyons, 2020). This will enhance public understanding and benefit future investments. Consequently, hybrid social entrepreneurship will reap substantial advantages from social investment, as individuals and community members will become more familiar with their businesses and offer support. Social investment might ultimately elevate the visibility of social enterprises, thereby expanding their customer base. Therefore, it is essential for hybrid social entrepreneurship to focus on generating social value for communities, possibly through their generosity and acting as philanthropists to enhance the social welfare of those communities. By making these efforts, a thorough or all-encompassing LED will come to realization. Even marginalized and predominantly underserved individuals and communities will significantly gain from the social initiatives led by hybrid social entrepreneurs.

Economic Value

The economic effect within the scope of the paper must be interpreted as the development of economic advancement intended

to improve the financial standing of people and communities. It pertains to the creation of new products, services, or processes or the creative reapplication of existing products, services, or processes that offer value (Brajevi, Babi, & Juki, 2015). In reality, the economic effect is associated with innovation in companies that launch new products and marketing approaches to enhance business productivity. Nevertheless, the economic influence on society will result in job creation for local residents. Staying true to the definition of hybrid social entrepreneurship social enterprises are recognized for creating an economic effect that may enhance the quality of life for people (Samuel, 2018; Nkabinde & Mamabolo, 2022). Thus, it is essential for the reader to grasp the definition of hybrid social entrepreneurship within the study's framework and prevent any misunderstandings regarding the study. Urbano, Toledano, and Soriano (2010) cited in Gupta, Chauhan, Paul, and Jaiswal (2020) argue that in contrast to charities, hybrid social enterprises generate income through their activities aimed at achieving social objectives. Concerning the economic effect, the primary funding source is the sale of products and services to clients, while grants offer additional financial support (Brajevi et al., 2015). The core aim of a social enterprise is to operate differently than a typical corporation, with profit maximization not being the goal (Squazzoni, 2009). Nonetheless, social enterprises need to generate revenue to ensure sustainability, distinguishing them from traditional charities that rely solely on external donations. Nonetheless, the economic effect of social enterprises is that they generate markets within both formal and informal business sectors.

The Inedible Repercussions of Liberal Capitalism

Liberal capitalism which is also referred to as economic capitalism refers to a political and economic philosophy that advocates for a market economy grounded in individualism and private ownership of production resources (Gissy, 2008). In the economic sphere, manufacturers supply products, not because they care for peoples' welfare, but rather to achieve financial gain. Moreover, in an unpleasant style of writing which is clear, Omeje (2021) asserts that capitalism in Africa is dysfunctional, as a result of a dysfunctional state. It is dysfunctional in the sense that capitalism has new versions evolved in postcolonial Africa, specifically: oligarchic capitalism, crony capitalism, hostage capitalism, predatory capitalism, and mafia capitalism. The biggest issue with dysfunctional capitalism is that it turns the economics of policy planning, choices, reforms, resource allocation, growth and development into pure nonsense and ridicule (Omeje, 2021). More recently, Omeje (2024) contends that the primary driving force behind dysfunctional capitalism in Africa is the personal gain of powerful elites through the direct or indirect seizure and exploitation of state authority. In dysfunctional capitalist systems, politics rarely focuses on production and service provision, but rather on "exploitation" or "wastefulness."

Clearly, economic (liberal) capitalism is only concerned with the pomposity of the bourgeoisie than tackling the social issues in the communities. Which means that the bourgeoisie is hesitant to invest in the tangible assets, machinery, social development and infrastructure of the real economy, which could uplift the living standards of the forgotten proletariat by both government and private sector. When highlighting persistent inequalities in South Africa as a result of capitalism, Hart and Padayachee (2013: 56) proffer that "What we have here is a 'world-class' business sector surrounded by human misery". Such an assertion could be proven to be true,

necessarily because the growing levels of poverty, inequality and unemployment continue to characterize and expose the weakness of the government and the private sector. In the context of this paper, liberal capitalism has become a foe to the success of LED. Because LED initiatives are concerned with uplifting the socially and economically forgotten individuals. For that reason, hybrid social entrepreneurship as a new form or version of capitalism may become the focal and integral catalyst for change in terms of arresting and reducing social and economic ills that have obliterated and killed the potential dreams and aspirations of the many South Africans.

Exploitation of Labour

Marx argues that to claim one group is exploited means that it engages in coerced, unpaid surplus (value)-producing labour for another group individual wealthiness (Fulmer, 2023). The contemporary application of the Marxist idea of labour and its linked theory of surplus value arises from the growing exploitation of workers by private capital within the current state and the government's worry about labour relations with employees (Casimir, Ezeani, & Nsiong, 2020). Meanwhile, history reveals harshly that Karl Marx, who is the champion of liberation and empowerment for the working class and the populace, has passed on for a long time, yet his legacy in the social sciences, sciences, and humanities continues to thrive to this day (Casimir et al., 2022). In the context of this paper, exploitation of labour is one of the setbacks that frustrates the farmworkers, domestic workers, mine workers and other individuals who are abused by liberal capitalism. Consequently, at times what employees give in with regard to the work they do is not adequately rewarded because liberal capitalism is only concerned with profits. Hence, the working and middle class continue to live an average life whilst the bourgeoisies is living a high-profile life at the expense of the working class. The system of exploiting labour perpetuates high levels of inequality in South Africa.

Crony Capitalism

Generally, crony capitalism is knotted with corruption. On the same breath, Khatri (2016: 3) shows that crony capitalism is “the deliberate, systematic use of public policy to rig markets in ways that benefit politically connected actors”. According to Diwan (2012), crony capitalism reduces the middle class's share and exacerbates inequality. Meanwhile, literature by Kırşanlı (2023) purports that crony capitalism fails to create enough job opportunities. Clearly, crony capitalism is an orchestrated activity by cronies in an attempt to weaken both public and private sectors. Due to crony capitalism, South Africa continues to endure painful hardships of poverty, inequality and unemployment. That is because of crony capitalism and corruption embedded in the state institutions, which weakens the capacity and ability of government to provide services to the people. Crony capitalism is used by those in power or positions of privilege to deny those not in power or of privilege decent living standards because of their pomposity and arrogance (Aligica & Tarko, 2015). Therefore, these inedible repercussions of liberal capitalism create inhumane milieu and reduce the dignity of ordinary people equivalent to nothingness.

Hybrid Social Entrepreneurship as a Catalyst for Local Economic Development

Numerous social and economic issues in developing nations like

Zimbabwe and Bangladesh, such as the growing gap between the rich and the impoverished, the aging population, and the fluctuating economy, have led to the emergence of social enterprises (Akhter, Hossain, & Asheq, 2020). The rise of social enterprises founded by hybrid social entrepreneurship is viewed as a solution that may uplift people's living standards and boost local economic development (LED). Consequently, the aim of hybrid social entrepreneurship is an essential strategy to address social and economic inequalities (Naruseb & Kalitanyi, 2024). Despite both public and private efforts, inequalities, poverty, and oppression persist in various nations.

Although the idea of hybrid social entrepreneurship is widely debated and understood in various ways, two main categories are emphasized in this context. The first category perceives social enterprises as Non-Profit Organisations (NPOs) that adopt a market-oriented approach (Chaudry, 2023). The alternative category perceives social enterprises as profit-driven organizations focused on achieving a social objective, encompassing two main facets: emphasizing the economic significance of supporting social initiatives and creating social value by addressing social issues (Ip, Wu, Liu, & Liang, 2017; Akhter et al., 2020; Peek, 2022). Hybrid social entrepreneurship involves sustainable businesses that combine commercial concepts to achieve social impact (Xanthopoulou & Sahinidis, 2023). The businesses may be Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) that implement business strategies to support their initiatives in pursuing the primary organizational objective of making a profit and promoting social benefits.

Even though hybrid social entrepreneurship is gaining visibility and drawing increased global interest, there is no widely accepted definition of the term, primarily due to an absence of a strong theoretical basis and the considerable influence of various contextual elements on the nature of hybrid social entrepreneurship projects (World Youth Report, n.d). Hybrid social entrepreneurship, an expanding area of research, not only promotes economic development but also provides a meaningful approach to social challenges and creates social advantages (Stoffers, Gunawan, & Kleefstra, 2018; Huda, Qodriah, Rismayadi, Hananto, Kardiyati, Ruskam, & Nasir, 2019; Faza, 2022). The growth of hybrid social entrepreneurship practitioners and policies has sparked greater interest in hybrid social entrepreneurship among scholars, yielding twofold advantages. Wang and Yee (2023) demonstrate that hybrid social entrepreneurship can aid marginalized communities in society while simultaneously fostering economic benefits. Hybrid social entrepreneurship, which combines the aim of tackling social problems with market-oriented approaches, does not eliminate the economic and social advantages produced, particularly for non-profit organizations (Wang & Yee, 2023). Peek (2022) argues that merging social and economic objectives in hybrid social entrepreneurship can distinguish between initiatives mainly centred on either the economic or social dimension.

Because they prioritize social and economic objectives, hybrid social entrepreneurship is regarded as a broader, more sustainable, charitable and innovative alternative to act as the catalyst of LED (Saebi, Foss, & Linder, 2019). Newbert and Hill (2014) consider hybrid social entrepreneurship an innovative venture designed to create surplus for producers by reducing negative externalities and promoting positive externalities through the integration of social and entrepreneurial aspects. In this paper, hybrid social entrepreneurs are characterized as often being for-profit ventures that employ

creativity (innovation) and technology to tackle significant societal issues such as injustice, poverty, illness, scarcity of water and other essentials, as well as environmental challenges through their profits. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) referenced by Gripp (2024) around fifty percent of participants engaged in significant social entrepreneurship activities choose to reinvest their earnings into the social goals set by their project, organization, or initiative. This reinvestment strategy emphasizes the essential principle of hybrid social entrepreneurship trends, which is to foster a cycle of positive change and lasting solutions through entrepreneurial efforts (Gripp, 2024).

Community Empowerment and Capacity Building

Empowerment signifies the level of control, influence and involvement that a community possesses regarding its own matters and choices, whereas capacity building involves enhancing the skills, knowledge, resources, and networks that a community requires to reach its objectives and maintain its activities (Veronica, Muhardi, & Suwarsi, 2023; cited in Hapsari & Hendayana, 2024). Therefore, hybrid social entrepreneurs are known to be philanthropists who have compassion or perhaps are passionate about the well-being of the community. This makes them different from traditional capitalists or entrepreneurs who solely focus on capital and profits, ignoring the social activities of the communities. Thus, hybrid social entrepreneurs have a zeal, zest and appetite to significantly contribute to community empowerment through tackling socio-economic challenges in the communities by creating employment, encouraging sustainable development practices, build social cohesion and building community resilient (Moridu, Doloan, Fitriani, Posumah, Rini, Hadiyati, Kune, & Yadasang, 2023). Hapsari and Hendayana (2024) come to an agreement that hybrid social entrepreneurship has demonstrated effectiveness as a strategy to tackle economic and social challenges impacting communities. To achieve lasting social influence, hybrid social entrepreneurship combines business ideas with societal goals. In executing hybrid social entrepreneurship numerous obstacles to community empowerment can emerge (Hapsari & Hendayana, 2024). Moreover, Achmad (2024) finds that hybrid social entrepreneurship can significantly address social issues, generate income and improve community well-being, proving to be an effective means for advancing sustainable development. Clearly, hybrid social entrepreneurs are a breath of fresh air in the capitalist society. As a point of recapitulation, hybrid social entrepreneurship represents a new form of capitalism that addresses both social and economic woes that make ordinary people in the communities look inhumane. To bring empowerment in the communities, hybrid social entrepreneurship may implement social programs such as environmental awareness, skills development programs and mentorship.

Discussion

When dissecting through literature, it is very vivid that liberal capitalism is a system of oppressing the poor and the proletariat. Capitalism on its own does not fully enhance human development because it is only concerned with individualism and profit maximization. Which means that liberal capitalism circumvents one of the pillars of LED, i.e., quality of life and social amenities. Thus, hybrid social entrepreneurs have demonstrated their strength as an effective means of boosting LED in South Africa. This is made

possible by having technological innovations in the business with the potential of growing the businesses and creating employment. By tackling unemployment, inequality, and sustainability issues, hybrid social entrepreneurs play a vital role as a new form of capitalism in creating resilient communities and promoting inclusive growth. Nonetheless, the complete potential of hybrid social entrepreneurship can only be achieved with enhanced participation, improved funding strategies, and more robust policy backing from both the public and private sectors. Hybrid social entrepreneurship is a vibrant movement that goes beyond the limits of conventional business frameworks. It can stimulate economic growth by tackling intricate issues with creative solutions.

Conclusion

As a point of recapitulation, social entrepreneurship is characterized by its twofold objective of creating social value and ensuring financial sustainability (Brinda et al., 2024). In contrast to traditional businesses, social enterprises underscore social impact in addition to profit, aiming to tackle societal challenges like poverty, inequality, and environmental harm (Brinda et al., 2024). In rural regions, where failures in the market and government shortcomings are more evident, social enterprises can significantly influence economic growth. By utilizing the 4IR technologies, local resources, encouraging community involvement and advancing sustainable practices, social entrepreneurs generate new avenues for income generation and social enhancement that are closely tied to the local context (Brinda et al., 2024). However, one may make an inference that hybrid social entrepreneurship may be a panacea to improve LED given the shortcomings of both the government and private sector. As it has been emphasized in the paper that hybrid social entrepreneurship may act as a new breed of capitalism that tackles social and economic woes. Thus, the work done by social entrepreneurs perhaps through their charity work, doing social activities and reinvesting their profit for the benefit of the marginalized and poor people should be supported to comprehensively improve LED.

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